

INTEGRATION OF TECHNOLOGY FOR QUALITY TEACHER EDUCATION

Dr. Rashmi Singh

Assistant Professor, Department of Education, S. S. Khanna Girls' Degree College
University of Allahabad

Abstract

This is the era of technology. Everything is technology-laden. This era is rightly called the era of the knowledge economy. This means that those who have more knowledge, updated knowledge in the right sense, are economically more powerful. Gone are the days when knowledge was transmitted from teacher to students in the four walls of the classroom only. With the advent of technology and the integration of ICT (Information and Communication Technology) in education, knowledge is rampant everywhere. Now it can be transmitted to several students within a fraction of a second. After technology integration, educational processes get speed, flexibility, accuracy, and accessibility. These four are the criteria of new-age educational quality benchmarks. In the present scenario, we cannot rely solely on traditional modes of practice. We have no option but to adopt technology-laden education for better, newer, faster, and more accessible educational practices in general and for teacher education in particular. If we look at the condition of teacher education institutions in the country, the condition is very poor. These institutions produce such graduates who are good for nothing. They have only a degree for name's sake and no updated knowledge, skills, and attitude to provide quality education to students. These graduates are not getting good teaching jobs because they are not market-ready. There is a mismatch between market demand and the skills these graduates possess (graduate attributes). Many such shortcomings of the traditional mode of teacher education institutions can be overcome by a judicious blend of technology in teaching-learning processes. This paper will deal with the integration of technology for quality and the issues and challenges that come in the way of its adoption. Even NEP 2020 has also put due emphasis on the adoption of technology at all educational levels, and especially for teacher education institutions.

Keywords: technology-laden, knowledge-economy, ICT, quality benchmarks, graduate attributes, integration of technology, NEP 2020.

Introduction:

Currently, we are living in a knowledge society, meaning knowledge is at the base of all the actions required in this society. In other words, one who knows is powerful and wealthy. In the words of an economist, data is the new oil of this technology-laden world, and skill sets are the new currency. Means skilled individuals who have updated knowledge can only survive and get a job in this digital era. Everything has been immersed in the wave of digitization and datafication. The recent pandemic has only intensified the spread of the use of technology in all facets of our lives. Inclusion of technology in our daily lives has changed the way we live, shop, travel, entertain, and even educate. Like other professionals, teachers, educators, and policymakers have also thought of integrating technology into educational practices to get the benefit from the immense potential of technology in the education sector. But this is not a simple and one-step process. Rather, it is a bit

tricky and complex. First of all, there is confusion around the term integration of technology into the classroom. Either teachers are reluctant to use technology in their classrooms (because of their fixed mindset), or they have a misconception that merely using PowerPoint presentations or an LCD projector in their classrooms is synonymous with successful technology integration, but actually integration of technology requires careful planning and can create desirable learning outcomes. So first of all, we have to understand the correct meaning of technology, educational technology, and what it means by successful integration of technology into the education system that can produce better-equipped learners.

Educational Technology:

Here, we deal with educational technology in its holistic view only. According to **Davies, Sprague, & New (2008)**, educational technology can be any tool, piece of equipment, or device, electronic or mechanical, that can be used to help students to accomplish specific learning goals. Educational technology includes both instructional technologies, which focus on technologies teachers employ to provide instruction, and learning technologies, which focus on technologies learners use to accomplish specific learning objectives. Educational technology is a combination of both instructional technology and learning technology in a broader sense. So by integration of technology, we mean that teachers can instruct effectively, and students can accomplish their specific learning goals with utmost ease. Educational technology, in its broadest sense, must be the backbone of any discipline in this globalized world.

Teacher Education:

Teacher education is that branch of the discipline that deals with the preparation of teachers. It is the most important type of discipline because each profession finds its basis in its teachers only. This is the noblest profession and must be flourished and nurtured in this way. But alas, it runs in the most pitiful state in our country. Even globally, it is a matter of discussion that the state of teacher education institutions must be rejuvenated to meet the challenges of the new digital era. As the older teaching generation is of a 'digital immigrants' nature and they have to deal with the students who are 'digital natives', i.e., born and brought up in this digital world, Generation Z, and now with the latest entry in this nomenclature, generation alpha, born roughly after 2010 (who grown up fully immersed in digital age). Hence, it is the need of the hour that teachers must put their best possible efforts to be digitally upgraded, because by nature our students are better equipped to deal with electronic gadgets. Therefore in a nutshell, we can say that in addition to the personal efforts of teachers, policy makers also have to take care of the required curriculum reforms in the field of teacher education, as it must have content as well as practicum embedded in sync with the technological advancement in the field of educational technology. National Education Policy 2020 has also emphasized the adoption of digital education, which will be taken in the later part of this discussion.

Need for Paradigm Shift in Pedagogy:

Paradigm shift is the most used term in the field of education nowadays. However, Thomas Kuhn has used 'paradigm change' instead of paradigm shift in his most influential book, "**The Structure of Scientific Revolutions**" (1962). According to Kuhn, a paradigm is a specific theoretical orientation, based upon a particular epistemology and research methodology, reflective of a particular scientific community at a particular time in history. As time progresses, the underpinning

philosophy of educational practices has also been changed, including its epistemology and research methodology, hence the need for a paradigm shift in pedagogy arises. Now in this digital world, the term pedagogy has been changed into andragogy (teaching-learning for adults), then to heutagogy (self-directed learning), and in general digigogy/ webogogy/ cybergogy, suitable for all sorts of learners in this digital world. Hence, the move towards digigogy from traditional pedagogy is urgently required. It is a paradigm shift in the pedagogical field. It is about designing a new framework for growth in the future of instruction. By following basic assumptions in the field of digital pedagogy (digigogy) teachers can interact with the digital natives, Gen ,Z and Gen Alpha in a much better way for desirable learning outcomes.

Training Teachers for New Millennium Competencies:

This is a new millennium and requires altogether different competencies for new-age teachers and for prospective teachers as well. Because prospective teachers will be teachers of the coming generation. There is additional responsibility on these teachers to be updated with all these new competencies to prepare such learners who will be competent enough in this fast-changing world with unprecedented challenges waiting at each next step. **Peters** (2003) goes beyond the need for training faculty in ICT issues and suggests considering the pedagogical changes derived from the arrival of the knowledge society, in which the use of ICT is implied. The next competencies that people, teachers, and students must have to face the challenges of the knowledge society are:

- Media Competence
- Competence in dealing productively with plurality
- Competence to deal productively with change
- Competence to active, conscious, and responsible life planning
- Social competence
- Communication competence
- Competence for collaboration
- Information competence
- Competence in knowledge management

Need for Pedagogically Sound Technology Integration Practices:

As it has already discussed, integration of technology does not mean merely using some technology here and there in classroom practices, but it has to be pedagogically sound too. This means that integration of technology must be in synchronization with the required pedagogical principles, too. There are many models available for pedagogically sound technology integration. From which TPACK model (Koehler and Mishra) sounds best for this purpose. This TPACK framework extends Shulman's idea of Pedagogical Content Knowledge. This model denies the intermixing of technology, content, and pedagogy in isolation; rather, it is based on the premise that the intersection of technology (technological content knowledge), content (pedagogical content knowledge), and pedagogy (technological pedagogical knowledge) creates such a space, which has technology, pedagogy, and content in a desirable manner and suits best this integration. So, it is based on three forms of knowledge, technological knowledge, content knowledge, and pedagogical knowledge, and rests on the complex interplay of these three basic knowledge forms. Another good model that describes how technology can be integrated into teaching and learning is the SAMR (Substitution, Augmentation, Modification, and Redefinition) model, proposed by Dr. R. Puentedura, in which the first two steps, i.e., substitution and augmentation comes under the

enhancement stage, and modification and redefinition come under the transformation stage. This model describes that educators must integrate technology as such in their instructional practices so that it not only substitutes the already existing tools with technological tools, but it must have the ability to redefine the instructional procedure and create tasks or outcomes that can be impossible without the use of technology; only this integration be said to be pedagogically sound.

UNESCO on Teacher Education:

UNESCO also recognizes the important role of teachers in the successful implementation of ICT in the educational process. This implementation, “will depend on the ability of teachers to structure the learning environment in non-traditional ways, to merge new technology with new pedagogy, to develop socially active classrooms, encouraging cooperative interaction, collaborative learning, and group work.” The UNESCO Planning guide for ICT in teacher education (Resta, 2002) cites three key principles for effective ICT development in teacher education that were put forward by the Society for Information Technology and Teacher Education (SITE). These principles are particularly pertinent for countries in the Asia-Pacific region looking for the most effective ways of integrating ICT in teacher education. The first principle is that technology should be infused into the entire teacher education program. It means that technology should not be used in isolation or in bits-but it should be part of the curricular philosophy of teacher education programmes. The second principle advanced by SITE is that technology should be introduced in context. It has been stated many times that teaching practices are always set in local, contextual settings, and only then will they produce maximum output. The third principle is that students should see their lecturers engaging in technology to present their subjects. And the last principle is about the engagement of technological practices in general instruction to prospective teachers.

UNESCO has recently established what they call Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) Competencies Standards for Teachers (CST). The UNESCO-ICT-CST project is based on three approaches:

- The technology literacy approach
- The knowledge deepening approach and
- The knowledge creation approach

NEP 2020 on Quality Teacher Education:

Integration of technology or adoption of digital education is embedded in the core value of NEP 2020 for all levels of Indian education to better equip learners with digital/ 21st century skills to deal with the new digital world. NEP 2020 has put more emphasis on the four-year integrated B.Ed for teacher education programmes. But here, our emphasis is on the integration of technology for transforming the general instruction into digitally enriched instruction. Because technology has immense potential in educational fields, it has made the trio of speed, accuracy, and accessibility of learning material available to its recipients. Nowadays, learners can get any information around the globe in a fraction of a second with the inclusion of ICT in education. Anyone with internet access can get any lecture or learning material provided on public domain, known as Open Educational Resources (OERs). The Government of India has also accepted the manifold usage of ICT in education and has launched its very own Study Webs of Active Learning for Young Aspiring Minds (SWAYAM) as a digital platform made by AICTE in 2016 to facilitate hosting of online courses to achieve three cardinal principles of educational policy, i.e., access, equity and quality. In

addition to it, NEP 2020 also talked about Digital Infrastructure for Knowledge Sharing (DIKSHA) platform for online training of teachers to be updated in the latest technological advancements. One more thing which has advocated so strongly in this policy regarding technology enabled instruction is, to ensure equitable use of technology between haves and have nots of technology holders. So that spread of technology in our daily lives and in educational practices must not widen the already existing digital divide. Equity must be the key factor. In this era it will be unfair if we do not talk about use of artificial intelligence (AI) in education. Artificial intelligence is the new buzz word in the field of education and it has immense potential to change the entire landscape of education. It can provide personalized and real time feedback to learners can keep the record of learning trajectory of each learner and can bring revolution in the field of educational assessments in the form of adaptive testing. It is high time that we bring AI in education ethically (as there may be more misuse than use of AI if used unethically) and make our prospective teachers better equipped with most up-to-date knowledge in the field of assessment-teaching-learning.

Barriers in Technology Integration:

It is evident now that technology integration is a must and we cannot deny it any more as educators, curriculum reformers and policy makers. But we are observing a poor state of affairs in the condition of successful technological integration. Pupil teachers are either not at all digitally upgraded or they are at the basic and first level of integration, i.e., substituting only a few traditional tools by technical tools. Why is it so? It has been found that there are several barriers (institutional as well as personal) in the integration of technology at both levels, instructional as well as learning. The most commonly observed barriers are:

- **Insufficient resources, including adequate access to technology and planning time:** India is still a developing nation and we spend a very less percent of our gross domestic product into the education sector. Hence in general our educational institutions face scarcity of resources and technological gadgets and their access to teachers. This is the most prominent barrier in technology integration.
- **Incomplete administrative support:** Where there is no such scarcity, there is incomplete, partial or not at all support from administrative level to incorporate new age technology in classroom or beyond the four walls of classroom. Without the administrative support no teacher can experiment any innovation by individual effort only.
- **Perceptions that technology is inconsistent with the traditional culture of the subject area:** Many teachers are still in the notion that only science and technical subjects demand for technological inclusion not for literary subjects. But it is clearly evident now that integration of technology is beneficial for attainment of learning outcomes of any discipline irrespective of its scope, nature and demand. This perception presents itself as another barrier.
- **Negative teacher attitude about technology:** Still there are teachers who do not have a positive attitude about the entry of technology in their instructional practices. This attitude prevents them from using any digital method in addition to traditional methods. This is the condition when you have resources but not the mindset to utilize it.
- **Lack of knowledge about and skills related to specific technologies, technology-supported pedagogy, and technology-related classroom management:** Last but not the least, if teachers have resources and mindset both, but not the required skills to use technological gadgets and programming due to lack of proper training, it seems the most rampant barrier in the integration of technology.

Strategies to Remove Barriers: Educators throughout the globe have a discussion over how to remove those barriers which create obstacles in the way of successful technology integration. These strategies can be

- **A shared vision for technology integration**
- **Empowered leaders**
- **Curriculum and policy support**
- **Access to hardware, software and other resources**
- **Skilled personnel and opportunities for professional development**
- **Technical assistance**
- **Appropriate teaching and assessment approaches**
- **Engaged communities: partnerships and collaboration**
- **Growth mindset of teachers**

Conclusion:

In a nutshell, it has been proved by researchers now that integration of technology is the backbone of quality teacher education programmes in this digital era throughout the globe. It has been discussed earlier that the basic philosophy of technology integration is not only adding a few technological tools in the classroom but it has to be part of the bone and flesh of the cross sectional curricular part of the teacher education program. It has to be pedagogically sound and the integration must follow basic psychological and ethical principles too. National as well as international policy makers have also taken into consideration principles as well as platforms for smooth transition into the digital world. There are many barriers at the institutional, administrative as well as personal level to create obstacles in the adoption of technology-laden instructional practices. But there are strategies too to remove these barriers and enrich and enhance the quality of teacher education programs in totality.

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